

WORK CULTURE AND LEARNING ORGANIZATION IN PROMOTING PRODUCTIVITY AMONG PUBLIC ELEMENTARY TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The study focused on the extent of work culture and learning organization in promoting productivity among public elementary teachers at the San Francisco district school system, division of San Pablo City for the School Year 2020-2021. A total of one hundred sixty-three (163) teacher-respondents were used in the study. Frequency percentage, standard deviation, and the weighted mean were used to assess the level of manifestations among variables. In addition, Pearson correlation and multiple regression were employed to identify predictors of work productivity. Findings revealed a moderated association exists between work culture and work productivity. Likewise, a moderate to strong correlation was seen between learning organization and work productivity. Furthermore, supportive work culture was seen as a predictor of effective teaching. Also, mental models and team learning were found as predictors of effective teaching. Lastly, innovative and bureaucratic work cultures were seen to be predictors of work commitment. Systems thinking, mental models, and personal mastery was also deemed as predictors of work commitment.

Keywords: Work Culture; Learning Organization; Work Productivity.